

MODELING SPATIAL VARIABILITY OF SOIL SALINITY USING LANDSAT REMOTE SENSING SATELLITE DATA

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Abstract

Soil salinization is a very common land degradation process, particularly in arid and semi-arid regions. Under harsh climatic conditions where evaporation is more than precipitation, soluble salts are accumulated in the soil, influencing soil properties with ultimate decline in productivity. In this study soil salinity prediction model is developed based on integrated satellite remote sensing data followed by site observations and geospatial methods. Different spectral indices including Simple Ratio, Normalize Difference Vegetation Index, Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index and Moisture Stress Index were calculated from original bands of Landsat images. Field survey was conducted in Shorkot, Punjab to collect the soil samples and were tested in lab. The results showed that maximum and minimum values of EC was 138.2 and 0.613 dSm⁻¹ respectively. Out of 31 samples 9 samples were found with EC value ≤ 4 and 22 samples represent the saline soils. Combining these satellite based indices and field EC variables into one model yielded the best fit with $R^2 = 0.89$. Out of the total area, 9.2% and 18% were identified as moderately and slightly saline, respectively. This shows that a very fine scale spatial variability analysis and modeling of surface soil salinity of large areas is possible using satellite remote sensing data.

INTRODUCTION

Soil salinity is the salt content in the soil and the process of increasing the salt content in the soil is known as salinization. Normally these salts are prominent at the soil surface. There can be several natural causes for variability in soil salinity i.e. the geological formations (parent material), soil type, landscape position, presence of brackish water table and due to high evaporation rates etc. (Clay et al., 2001; Shi et al., 2005; Guo et al., 2015 and Stadler et al., 2015). Beside these natural factors, manmade activates i.e. use of fertilizers can also cause the soil

salinity. The saline soils usually resulted in decrease of the land value and productivity of many areas all over the globe (Elhag, 2016). Generally the salinity occurs in irrigated soils due to improper irrigation practices (Szabolcs, 1986; Zaccaria et al., 2016) and lack of drainage which led to accumulation of salts in the soil in concentrations, which are harmful to crops (Rengasamy, 2006 and Peck, 1978).

The main problem of salinity is in arid and semi-arid regions where it is considered as a major form of land degradation in agricultural soils (Williams, 1999; Allbed and Lalit, 2013 and Re and Sacchi, 2017). The conditions are even worse in countries like Pakistan where agriculture is the largest economic sector and majority of the population is directly or indirectly depending on it. In Pakistan, about 15.6 million acres of land are salt-affected and of which 4.7 million acres is saline, 4.5 and 2.5 million acres is pervious and impervious saline-sodic respectively (Qureshi et al., 1998; Farooq et al., 2013 and Qureshi, 2016). Major part of the affected soils are present in Sindh and then in Punjab province of Pakistan. So this is very important for Pakistan to have appropriate and updated information about the extent and magnitude of soil salinity for better planning and execution of soil reclamation programs. Soil salinity is usually measured through electrical conductivity (EC) in soil saturated paste (EC_p), its liquid extract (EC_e), or by different soil to water mixtures (Sonmez et al., 2008). Soils with an $EC_e > 4$ dSm^{-1} is referred to as saline (Coppola et al., 2016, Chhabra, 1996 and Bharti et al., 2017). EC_e is considered as one of the best soil quality assessment parameters as cited in literature (Douaik et al., 2004; Cetin et al., 2012; Cetin and Cevat, 2003). Regular monitoring of soil salinity is important for effective management soil, water and agricultural lands (Akramkhanov et al., 2011, Dumanski and C1, 2000). Several soils are spatially very variable, as salinity vary quickly over small distances relative to landscape and other reasons (Shrivastava and Rajesh, 2015; Moffett et al., 2010 and Vandenbruwaene et al., 2015). Therefore, for the quantification and accurate assessment of saline soils are majorly depend on the number of soil samples collected in the field and tested in the laboratory. On the other hand the conventional laboratory methods for soil salinity measurement are time taking and costly. To overcome the cost of widespread sampling, most of the studies have utilized remotely sensed (RS) data/images to identify

and quantify soil salinity. Specially, saline soils are associated with different spectral wavelengths and band ratios like soil and vegetation based indices (Khan et al., 2005; Ben-Dor et al., 2009; Yong-Ling et al., 2010; Fernandez-Buces et al., 2006; Lugassi et al., 2017; Rocha Neto et al., 2017; Marchesini et al., 2016). These techniques have their limitations because of spatial and spectral resolution of the satellite images and atmospheric effects (Moran et al., 1997 and Lillesand et al., 2014) but they can be reduced/removed by using current advance algorithms and combination of the indices with field data.

In this study we have used the recently launched Landsat 8, satellite data which is launched by NASA, USA. Landsat 8 carries two type of sensors: 1) the operational land imager (OLI) and 2) the thermal infrared sensor (TIRS). The specifications of the sensors on are given in table I.

Keeping the devastating effects of salinity on soil and costly procedures to measure it this study was designed with the objective to map and model spatial variability of soil salinity over a large agricultural region in Shorkot Pakistan, using satellite based information.

RESULTS

EC Data

The lab analysis of soil samples shows that the maximum and minimum values of EC was 138.2 and 0.613 dSm^{-1} respectively. As per literature the soils with EC value > 4 is considered as saline soils whereas out of 31 samples 9 samples were found with EC value ≤ 4 and 22 samples represent the saline soils (figure 8).

Salinity Mapping

Soil salinity present in the study were mapped using the satellite based indices and the field survey. The indices SR, NDVI, SAVI and MSI were reclassified into saline and non-saline areas based on threshold values derived from literature and adjusted as per field collected data (Amukali, Lobell, Zhang, Elhag). The threshold value for SR; NDVI; SAVI and MSI was from 0.48 to 0.71; 0.36 to

0.8; -0.31 to 0.84 and 0.42 to 0.79 respectively. Several The maps for all the saline areas are shown in figure 9 (a-d).

The final saline map (figure 10) was developed by extracting high saline areas from each saline map of band rationing images.

The field based EC data was overlaid on the final saline map and the results shows a good relationship between the

Spatial Modeling of Soil Salinity

The EC free from multicollinearity problem were used as input in developing linear regression equation. A 'stepwise' method (Montgomery et al., 2015) was used in SAS for selection of variables. The resulting regression based on remote sensing and field measurement of EC is given as equation 1:

$$EC = 173.146 - (48.813 \times SR) - (188.895 \times MSI) + (10.909 \times NDVI) - (7.864 \times SAVI)$$

To calculate the closeness of the data fitness of the data the value of R, R_{sqf} and Adj R_{sqf} are 0.89, 0.80 and 0.77 respectively. The value of R represents that model is good to predict 89% of soil salinity using the satellite derived indices i.e. SR, MSI, NDVI and SAVI.

The map (figure 11) shows the field EC data on the highly saline areas as identified from the satellite based indices. It clearly indicates that more than 83 % of the saline points with EC greater than 4 falls in high saline areas.

DISCUSSION

A very fine scale spatial variability analysis and modeling of surface soil salinity of large areas is possible using satellite remote sensing data. The model developed on the basis of satellite remote sensing based indices i.e. SR, MSI, NDVI and SAVI, followed by site observations can be an alternative to the traditional methods for determining soil salinity in the areas. This combined model is proved to be a promising tool over other developed model because of its simplicity, satellite data efficiency and acceptable degree of accuracy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

Shorkot is a city in the Punjab, Pakistan located at 30°30'N and 72°24'E with

an altitude of 131 meters as shown in figure 1. The climate of Shorkot site is dry subtropical. Usually two type of seasons are well known there i.e. a hot summer with late monsoon rains and a relatively milder winter. Average rainfall per year is around 200-250 mm. Salinity is a major problem in the area which is the reason for decline in agricultural production.

Soil Sampling and Laboratory Analysis

The surface soils (0-6 cm) were collected via random stratified sampling in the study area as shown in figure 2. At each site, soils were sampled with hand auger and placed in sealed plastic bags for transport back to the laboratory. The location of all sampling sites were geo-referenced with a *Garmin e-Trex* (Garmin Ltd., Schaffhausen, Switzerland) global positioning system receiver (location error approx. ±5 m).

Laboratory analyses were conducted in the Saline Agriculture Research Center, Institute of soil and Environmental sciences, University of Agriculture Faisalabad. Upon arrival, samples were air dried and lightly ground to pass a 2 mm sieve prior to all other analyses. Soil EC (1:5) were determined in a 1:5 (v/v) soil water slurry using 20 g soil and 100 ml distilled water. After an equilibration time of two hours, the saturation paste was filtered under suction. The electrical conductivity was determined on the filtrate with the TOA Model CM-14P electrical conductivity meter.

Acquisition and Pre-Processing of Satellite Data

Landsat 8 operational land imager (OLI) data for year 2016 were downloaded, stacked and then were subset to Shorkot as area of interest (AOI) as shown in figure 3. After sub-setting the pre-processing of satellite images i.e. atmospheric, radiometric and geometric corrections was done as this is very important and pre-requisite before further usage of the satellite data.

After the pre-processing different band rationing techniques were applied on satellite images to calculate the four indices including Simple Ratio (SR), Normalize Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Soil

Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI) and Moisture Stress Index (MSI).

Simple Ratio (SR)

The SR used two spectral bands Red and Near Infrared (NIR) to indicate the amount of vegetation or greenness in the area (figure 4). The formula for SR is given as under:

$$SR = \frac{RED}{NIR}$$

RED and NIR are the response of the ground in the red and near-infrared spectral bands respectively. Higher the value of SR means more will be the greenness (vegetation) and vice versa.

Normalize Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI)

The NDVI was applied to delineate the vegetation from other land features present in the study area. The NDVI value range from -1 to +1, where the positive i.e. $NDVI \geq 0.3$ is green vegetation with 95% confidence level. The formula for NDVI is given as under:

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR-RED}{NIR+RED}$$

NIR and RED are the response of the ground in the near-infrared and red spectral bands respectively. In our study area the maximum and the minimum values of NDVI was 0.85 and 0.2 respectively as shown in figure 5. The positive values represent the green area i.e. the area with vegetation cover.

Soil Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI)

The SAVI is also similar to the NDVI but with the addition of a soil brightness correction factor L as in areas where vegetative cover is low (i.e., < 50%) and the soil surface is exposed, the reflectance of light in the red and near-infrared spectra can influence vegetation index values. The formula to calculate the SAVI is given as following equation:

$$SAVI = \frac{NIR-RED}{NIR+RED+L} \times 1 + L$$

Where NIR and RED are the near infrared and red bands of the spectrum and L is the soil brightness correction factor. The value of L varies by the amount of green vegetation as if vegetation is very high the value of L will be 0; and in areas with no green vegetation L will be 1. As shown in figure 6 the values of SAVI varies from +0.97 to -0.41 in the Shorkot region.

Moisture Stress Index (MSI)

The MSI is a reflectance measurement that is sensitive to water content. As the water content of leaves in soil and vegetation increases, the strength of absorption around $1.59 \mu\text{m}$ (short wave infrared, SWIR band) increases. The higher values of MSI indicates greater water stress and less water content. The formula to calculate the SAVI is given as following equation:

$$MSI = \frac{SWIR}{NIR}$$

Where SWIR and NIR are the Short Wave Infrared and Near Infrared respectively. The maximum and minimum values of MSI in Shorkot were found to be 0.88 and 0.2 respectively (figure 7).

After calculation of all these indices the index raster's were further reclassified into saline and non-saline areas on the basis of thresholds given in literature (Iqbal, 2011; Zewdu et al., 2015; Mehra et al., 2017 and Rozario et al., 2016).

Development of Spatial Regression Model

Different analyses, which involve remote sensing based indices (SR, NDVI, SAVI and MSI) development along with field based data was used to develop GIS assisted regression model. The results of the model was then used to assess its suitability to map soil salinity directly from the soil, and indirectly from remote sensing based indices.

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Table I: The spectral and spatial resolution of Landsat 8 sensor.

Sr. No	Spectral Band Name	Bandwidth (µm)	Resolution (m)
1	Band 1 Coastal	0.43 - 0.45	30
2	Band 2 Blue	0.45 - 0.51	30
3	Band 3 Green	0.53 - 0.59	30
4	Band 4 Red	0.63 - 0.67	30
5	Band 5 NIR	0.85 - 0.88	30
6	Band 6 SWIR 1	1.57 - 1.65	30
7	Band 7 SWIR 2	2.11 - 2.29	30
8	Band 8 Pan	0.50 - 0.68	15
9	Band 9 Cirrus	1.36 - 1.38	30
10	Band 10 TIRS 1	10.6 - 11.19	30 (100)
11	Band 11 TIRS 2	11.5 - 12.51	30 100)

Fig. 1: Map of study area.

Fig. 2: Soil sampling locations of the field survey.

Fig. 3: False color composite subset of Landsat 8 satellite image for Shorkot region.

Fig. 4: Simple Ratio (SR) map of Shorkot region highlighting the vegetation in green color.

Fig. 5: NDVI map of Shorkot region highlighting the vegetation and other land in transition from green to red color.

Fig. 6: SAVI map of Shorkot region highlighting the exposed soil surface and vegetation cover.

Fig. 7: MSI map of Shorkot region highlighting the areas with high and low moisture content.

Fig. 8: Spatial distribution of soil samples with respect to their EC values.

Fig. 9: Soil salinity maps derived from band rationing images.

Fig. 10: Final soil salinity map of Shorkot region.

Fig. 11: Soil salinity map overlaid with factual EC dataset.